

THE LONG-RUN RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN EXPENDITURE ON EDUCATION AND GROSS DOMESTIC PRODUCT IN INDIA: CO-INTEGRATION ANALYSIS

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Abstract

Education plays predominant role in development of any country. Investment in education has higher return than physical investment. The present paper examined the long-run relationship between expenditure on education and GDP of India. The study used secondary time series data with appropriate econometric models like Johansen co-integration and VECM. It has been found from the study that the variables represent education expenditure and economy have shown significant positive trends which is warranted. There have been long-run stable relationships between expenditures on education and GDP. Accordingly, education expenditure is co-integrating with GDP. The panel co-integration further decomposed and found that only capital expenditure is having co-integrating vector, the other expenditures; revenue and total expenditure on education are not having co-integrating vectors. It is found from VEC model that second period capital expenditure corrects the errors in equilibrium with GDP by 30 percent. The first period GDP corrects the short-term disturbances in the long-run relationship with Capital expenditure only by 4 percent. Therefore, it is the capital expenditure on education will restore the relationship with GDP in the long-run. Hence, the study once again argues that the governments have to give more important to education to build the human capital to have strong economy.

Keywords: *Education, Human Capital, Economy, Co-integration and Error Correction*

Introduction:

Education plays predominant role in development of any country. Theoretically and empirically it has been proved that the education has significant role in economic development and economic development also significantly influence the quality and level of education. Most of the developed countries are also known for their quality of education. The World Bank in its report on infrastructure has proved the positive relationship between education and development. Gary Becker (Becker, 1964, 1975 & 1993) and Schultz (Schultz, 1971), have proved that the investment in education has higher return than physical investment. In this

background, in the present paper an attempt has made to establish the long-run relationship between expenditure on education and Gross Domestic Product (GDP)

Review of Literature:

Schultz (Schultz, 1971), Mincer (Mincer, 1962), Renshaw (Renshaw, 1960), Murphy and Welch (Murphy & Welch, 1993), Shaffer (Shaffer, 1961), Solow (Solow, 1965), Spengler (Spengler, 1950), Romer (Romer, 1986) and Lucas in 1988 (Robertson, 2002), and other are pioneers in human capital research, have congregated to lay down the theoretical foundation for unconventional human capital approach which was not the part of discipline of economics. However, Becker remains as the empire of the theory of human capital (Shackleton, 1981). Accordingly, the present study is largely based on the theoretical works of Gary Becker.

Methodology:

The present study has used secondary time series data for the period from 2005-06 to 2020-21. The major variables considered for the study are; revenue, capital and total expenditure on education and to represent the economy the GDP has been considered. Since the data is in time series, the unit root test has conducted to verify the stationarity of data using Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) Test. The Johansen procedure has used to establish the long-run relationship. Vector Error Correction Model (VECM) has used to examine the short time dynamics in the long-run relationship. The diagnostic test are also conducted to verify the normality, serial correlation and heteroscedasticity.

Results and Discussion:

The status of expenditure on education in India and GDP of India has presented. At the same time, the growth in revenue expenditure, capital expenditure, and total expenditure on education and also the growth of GDP also presented.

Table 1: Expenditure on Education and GDP of India

(At current prices in Crore)

Description	Revenue	Capital	Total	GDP
Average	326933.2	373193.4	381270.2	11348284
CAGR	10.22	51.74	11.11	12.10
t-ratio	13.870	6.737	10.19	36.02
Sig	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000

Source: Budget Documents, GOI.

The expenditure on education and GDP of India are presented above. It is found from the table that during the period from 2005-06 to 2020-21, the average revenue expenditure on education was 326933 crore, the capital expenditure was 373193 crore, the total expenditure

on education (both centre and states) was 381270 crore. During the same period the average GDP of India was 11348284 crore. The growth in revenue expenditure on education was 10.22 percent and it is significant. The growth in capital expenditure is 51.74 percent and it is significant. The growth of total expenditure on education was 11.11 percent. The growth of GDP was 12.10 percent and it is also significant. All the values are in current prices and therefore, the growths are seems to be at higher side. The capital expenditure was very low during 2005-06 and 2011-12 and increased in the successive years. Hence, growth of capital is high. It has been clear from the growth rates that all the variables have shown significant positive trends which is warranted.

The following graph shows the trends in expenditure on education and GDP of India.

Graph 1: Expenditure on Education and GDP

Table 2: Stationarity of Data

Variable	t- test value	P-value	Model	Level
Revenue	-3.432	0.028	With Constant	$I \sim (1)$
Capital	-3.372	0.003	None	$I \sim (1)$
Total	-3.807	0.001	None	$I \sim (1)$
GDP	-4.426	0.001	None	$I \sim (2)$

Source: Researcher computed the results by using actual data.

The test of stationarity has conducted by using Augmented Dickey-Fuller procedure.

The revenue expenditure is integrated of order one with constant model. Capital and total

expenditure are integrated of order one with the model without constant and trend. GDP is integrated of order two with the model without constant and trend. Therefore, all the variables used in this analysis are non-stationary at level and found stationary with first and second differences. Accordingly, the Johansen procedure is used to find the long-run relationship between expenditure on education and GDP.

Table 3: Co-integration Test for Expenditure on Education and GDP

Hypothesized		Trace	0.05	
No. of CE(s)	Eigen value	Statistic	Critical Value	Prob.**
None *	0.990593	109.2482	55.24578	0.0000
At most 1 *	0.888326	43.91932	35.01090	0.0044
At most 2	0.482424	13.22895	18.39771	0.2273
At most 3 *	0.248982	4.008566	3.841466	0.0453
Trace test indicates 3 co-integrating eqn(s) at the 0.05 level				
* denotes rejection of the hypothesis at the 0.05 level				
**MacKinnon-Haug-Michelis (1999) p-values				

Source: Researcher computed the results by using actual data.

The Johansen test has used to estimate the long-run relationship among revenue, capital, total expenditure on education and GDP in India. It has been found from the co-integration test that the trace has identified 3 co-integrating equations. Means, there are three long-run relationship among the variables used in this analysis. Accordingly, there have been long-run stable relationships between expenditures on education and GDP. Therefore, expenditure on education and GDP in India will go together. Accordingly, education expenditure is co-integrating with GDP. The panel co-integration further decomposed and found that only capital expenditure is having co-integrating vector, the other expenditures; revenue and total expenditure on education are not having co-integrating vectors. Therefore, the total expenditure on education is not co-integrating with GDP. Meaning, the total expenditure on education is not going with GDP. Hence, there is a need to give importance to education in India to enhance the human capital formation.

Table 3: VECM Test for Expenditure on Education and GDP

Error Correction:	D(CAPITAL)	D(GDP)
CointEq1	-0.772668	0.826420
	(0.38725)	(1.00396)
	[-1.99529]	[0.82316]
D(CAPITAL(-1))	0.062622	0.128673
	(0.36456)	(0.94514)
	[0.17178]	[0.13614]
D(CAPITAL(-2))	-0.035109	-0.297649
	(0.32003)	(0.82970)
	[-0.10971]	[-0.35874]
D(GDP(-1))	-0.036754	0.417570
	(0.14031)	(0.36375)
	[-0.26195]	[1.14795]
D(GDP(-2))	0.323662	0.051267
	(0.14986)	(0.38851)
	[2.15981]	[0.13196]
C	-265314.9	729368.3
	(164961.)	(427670.)
	[-1.60835]	[1.70545]
R-squared	0.586334	0.628453

Source: Researcher computed the results by using actual data.

The Vector Error Correction (VEC) model has been used to find the short term dynamics in the long-run relationship and to identify the variable which responsible to restore the relationship between Capital expenditure on education and GDP in India. As mentioned in the previous section; revenue expenditure on education and total expenditure on education are not co-integration with GDP. Hence, the VECM has computed only for capital expenditure on education and GDP. It is found from the VEC that first period Capital expenditure not corrects the short-term disturbances in the long-run relationship with GDP. Second period capital expenditure corrects the errors in equilibrium with GDP by 30 percent. The first period GDP corrects the short-term disturbances in the long-run relationship with Capital expenditure only by 4 percent. Therefore, it is the capital expenditure on education will restore the relationship

with GDP in the long-run. Hence, the study once again argues that the governments have to give more important to education to build the human capital to have strong economy.

The needed diagnostic tests are also conducted to support the above results and make them reliable. Jarque-Bera Normality Tests was conducted and found that the JB stat is insignificant (p: 0.609) to reject the null hypothesis; Normality. VEC Residual Serial Correlation LM Tests was conducted and found that the LM stat is insignificant (p: 0.801) to reject the null hypothesis; No Serial Correlation. VEC Residual Heteroscedasticity Tests was conducted and found that the joint chi-square value is insignificant (p: 0.339) to reject the null hypothesis; No Heteroscedasticity.

Conclusion:

The present paper examined the long-run relationship between expenditure on education and GDP of India. It has been found from the study that the variables represent education expenditure and economy have shown significant positive trends which is warranted. There have been long-run stable relationships between expenditures on education and GDP. Accordingly, education expenditure is co-integrating with GDP. The panel co-integration further decomposed and found that only capital expenditure is having co-integrating vector, the other expenditures; revenue and total expenditure on education are not having co-integrating vectors. It is found from VEC model that second period capital expenditure corrects the errors in equilibrium with GDP by 30 percent. The first period GDP corrects the short-term disturbances in the long-run relationship with Capital expenditure only by 4 percent. Therefore, it is the capital expenditure on education will restore the relationship with GDP in the long-run. Hence, the study once again argues that the governments have to give more important to education to build the human capital to have strong economy.

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